

References

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**Addition-Elimination Reactions of
4- and 6-Chloroindolin-2,3-diones with
Aromatic Amines**

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IN continuation of our work¹ on addition-elimination reactions of 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (1a, b), we report herein the nucleophilic addition-elimination reactions of 1a and b with aromatic amines.

Nucleophilic attack of anilines on 4- and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (1a, b) underwent smoothly leading to 4a and b in excellent yields. 1a and 1b were treated with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic KOH to get the corresponding 1-methyl analogs which were again treated with anilines leading to 3a and 3b respectively. Further, Mannich condensation on 4a and 4b resulted in the formation of 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-4/6-chloro-3-

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{KOH}-\text{EtOH}$, (ii) $\text{R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2$ (p), (iii) morpholine/piperidine/ HCHO .

(phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5a and 5b), which provided additional evidence for the structures of 4a and 4b (Scheme 1). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Mass spectrum of compound 6 showing characteristic chlorine profile was in conformity with the assigned structure (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

4-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(arylimino)-2-indolinones (3a) 4-Chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) was refluxed with *p*-chloroaniline (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The orange crystals separated on cooling were dried and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

6-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(arylimino)-2-indolinones (3b): The compounds were prepared by condensing 6-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) with *p*-chloroaniline (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The crystals that separated on cooling were filtered, dried and recrystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

4-Chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (4a): A mixture of 4-chloroisatin (1.81 g, 0.01 mol) and substituted-aniline (0.01 mol) in methanol (15 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid product was washed with methanol.

Similarly, other compounds were prepared using different anilines (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF 4/6-CHLORO-3-(SUBSTITUTED-PHENYLIMINO)-2-INDOLINONES (3-5)*

Sl. no.**	Compd. no.	R	X	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1.	3a	Cl	-	57	197-200	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
2.	4a	H	-	64	225	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O
3.	4a	Cl	-	71	240	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
4.	4a	OCH ₃	-	60	185-90	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂
5.	5a	H	CH ₂	66	165	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O
6.	5a	Cl	O	68	165	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
7.	5a	Cl	CH ₂	63	165-67	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
8.	5a	OCH ₃	O	62	128-30	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂
9.	5a	OCH ₃	CH ₂	67	125	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂
10.	3b	Cl	-	57	144	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
11.	4b	H	-	71	190	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ O
12.	4b	Cl	-	68	220-22	C ₁₄ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
13.	4b	OCH ₃	-	66	218	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂
14.	5b	H	O	59	210d	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂
15.	5b	H	CH ₂	56	220d	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O
16.	5b	Cl	O	73	147	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
17.	5b	Cl	CH ₂	62	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
18.	5b	OCH ₃	O	60	158	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₂
19.	5b	OCH ₃	CH ₂	62	195	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ ClN ₂ O ₂

*Satisfactory C, H analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

**For sl. nos. 1-9, Y = 4-Cl; for sl. nos. 10-19, Y = 6-Cl.

6-Chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (4b): The compounds were prepared by using 6-chloroisatin and different anilines (Table 1).⁵

4-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5a): 4-Chloro-3-substituted-phenylimino-2-indolinone (0.01 mol) was suspended in methanol (20 ml) and warmed on a water-bath and then formalin (1 ml) and morpholine (1 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring and kept at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid was washed with methanol, dried and recrystallised from CHCl₃-petroleum ether (b.p. 80-100°).

Similarly, other morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs were synthesised; ν_{max} compd. sl. no. 5: 2920 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 790 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 6: 2940 (CH₂), 1740 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 790 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 7: 2940 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1600 (C=N) and 770 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 8: δ 2.43 (4H, N (CH₂)₂), 3.52 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 4.21 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.78-7.22 (7H, ArH); compd. sl. no. 9: δ 2.50 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.60 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 3.78 (3H, OCH₃), 4.32 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.8-7.3 (7H, ArH); compd. sl. no. 10: δ 2.40 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.70 (3H, OCH₃), 4.22 (2H, NCH₂N) and 6.7-7.2 (7H, ArH).

6-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (5b): The compounds were prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-3-(substituted-phenylimino)-2-indolinones (Table 1); ν_{max} compd. sl. no. 16: 2840 (CH₂),

1725 (C=O), 1595 (C=N) and 850 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 17: 2910 (CH₂), 1730 (C=O), 1590 (C=N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 18: 2840 (CH₂), 1710 (C=O), 1580 (C=N) and 830 cm⁻¹ (CCl); compd. sl. no. 19: 2940 (CH₂), 1720 (C=O), 1610 (C=N) and 820 cm⁻¹ (CCl)

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Reference

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Synthesis of some New Isonicotinoylazopyrazoles

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THE chemistry of isoniazide and pyrazoles has been very extensively studied because many drugs include these rings¹. Similarly, biological importance of azo compounds is well-known². In

